

THEORETICAL BASES OF PREPARATION OF FUTURE ENGINEERS FOR RESEARCH ACTIVITY, FORMS AND METHODS OF SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE

O.S.Nurova

*Karshi engineering-economics Institute, 180100,
Karshi, Uzbekistan*

Abstract. This article discusses the theoretical foundations of preparing future engineers for research activities, forms and methods of scientific knowledge, the need for systematic work to develop research skills and increase the level of independence for students to successfully master scientific methods and use them as new learning tools.

Keywords; research, hypothesis testing, laboratory, cognitive activity, systematic research, intuitive, experiment, scientific cognitive cycle, empirical and theoretical methods, reproductive, communicative.

By analyzing the literature on students' research activities, M.V.Klarin comes to the following conclusion: "Ready-made conclusions offered for mastering ... the impression of completeness and uncertainty of knowledge. Saving time, concise presentation of information The most important feature of knowledge is its relative nature, causes mobility ... "[54]. In doing so, he points out that in recent decades, consistent research in this area has lagged behind educational research presented in the form of laboratory work. Common features of these areas are: problem identification, problem formulation, explanation of problem details, hypothesis formation, action planning and development, data collection, data and conclusions comparison, data preparation and writing, data presentation, review of results in the process of answering questions, test a hypothesis, generate data, draw conclusions.

J.Zuxman proposes a model aimed at mastering the experience of systematic research and includes the following activities: data collection, interpretation, analysis of research [159].

VG Razumovsky drew attention to some features of the process of cognitive activity in solving creative tasks. First, he sees the research task as one of the manifestations of educational and creative tasks. A learning-creative task is a task that is performed on the basis of knowledge of the basic laws, but formed within the framework of a specific requirement that does not directly reflect the events whose laws must be used in solving this problem [113]. Our research will cover research and development tasks.

Second, V.G.Razumovskiy A. Special attention is paid to the process of scientific cognition noted by Einstein: “fact-model-experiment-result” (Fig. 1).

In accordance with the cycle of scientific knowledge, the learning process must be built according to the logic of scientific knowledge: from evidence to hypotheses and from experimental results to hypotheses. At each stage of the scientific knowledge cycle, there is a correlation between logical and intuitive

mental actions. For students, this model is a way to get subjectively new information. Therefore, the following conditions should be taken into account: the choice of tasks that are difficult for students, but purposeful, the interest of students in solving the problem. The systematization of increasingly complex tasks is carried out taking into account their reliance on general professional disciplines and the interdependence of content. The proposed tasks should have a theoretical or practical orientation.

Scientific knowledge (and knowledge as a result) is a process, that is. an integral evolving system of knowledge, the main element of which is theory - the highest form of knowledge organization.

Systematic work is needed to develop research skills and increase the level of independence for students to successfully master scientific learning methods and use them as a new means of learning. This is clearly seen in Table 1, which compares the cycle of scientific knowledge and the stages of student performance in solving a problem.

Taking into account the goal setting and planning of independent learning activities, independent learning activities are formed through deep and meaningful mastery of the basics of science by students, the acquisition of information skills and the application of knowledge in practice [137].

Table 2

The cycle of	Stages of working on the task
1. Putting the problem on the basis of observations	1. Identify and understand the problem situation 2. Identify the problem and formulate it
2. Study the problem	1. Identify existing analog objects associated with the identified problem and solve it at a certain quality level
3. Formulation of the working hypothesis	1. Identify conflicts and formulate tasks, address deficiencies in resolving them, and meet
4. Theory development (logical and mathematical	1. Select the optimal solution 2. Analyze and explain the decision

<p>5. Planning and experimental testing of a new theory</p>	<p>1. 1. Determining the operating modes of the object, its technological and operational parameters</p> <p>2. 2. Design, development, implementation of the conditions and mechanism of experimental testing</p>
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Different aspects of independent work of students were studied by V.I.Andreev [5], V.K.Buryak [23], M.A.Danilov [39], N.I.Pidkasist [102]. N.A.Polovnikov [107] and others classify independent work on different bases:

- according to the didactic purpose - cognitive, practical, generalizing;
- cognitive, creative, research, etc. by type of task;
- reproductive, reproductive-research-creative;
- according to the nature of communicative influence - collective, group, individual;
- outside the audience;
- Theoretical, experimental, modeling, design, observation, classification, generalization, systematization according to scientific methods of knowledge.

Based on the analysis, we can identify specific elements of independent work:

- availability of assignments in various forms (abstracts, reports, tasks, computational and graphic work, course projects);
- student's choice of research topic and task;
- indirect involvement of the teacher in the management of the task for students (indirect management of the student's learning activities by the teacher);
- availability of specially provided time and possible place for performance (practical training, laboratory seminar, individual consultations, etc.).

Given the sequence of formation of independent cognitive activity, many researchers distinguish four levels of its formation (P.I.Pidkasist and M.L.Portnov [102, p. 212]):

- 1) reproductive: reproduction, the transformation of a particular method into something similar;
- 2) reconstructive-variable: modernization of a certain method in a non-standard situation;
- 3) partial research: combining several known methods to solve a new problem in a non-standard situation;
- 4) research: creating a new way to solve a problem situation.

Each level has its own characteristics of goal setting and planning: first, the student plans research under the guidance of a teacher; second, the teacher identifies the problem and the research goal, and the student plans and conducts the research himself; third, the student sets a goal and plan within the scope of the task presented by the teacher; fourth, the student conducts research activities on his or her own initiative and independently. In the future, we will follow this classification of levels of students' research activities.

Cognition as a method of activity involves the use of a specific set of forms and processes used by a person to achieve cognitive goals [48]. In our study, we consider four main forms of scientific knowledge: scientific fact, hypothesis, law and theory, and empirical and theoretical methods of scientific knowledge.

Table 2 shows the system of forms of scientific knowledge.

From a philosophical point of view, "method (Greek-research, cognition, theory, teaching method) is a form of practical and theoretical assimilation of truth based on the laws of motion of the object under study, the system of regulatory principles of transformational practice or cognitive theoretical activity" [146].

Table 2

Sci	Brief description	Brief description Elements of knowledge
entifickn nowledge	Elements of knowledge	
Sci entificfa ct	A reliable form of knowledge that serves as a starting point in the formulation and solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •• formofknowledge; •• knowaboutreality; •• reliability; •• empiricalorthoretical;
Sci entificH ypothesi sScientif icAssum	ScientificHypothesi sScientificAssumption [148]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •• adequacyandcompliance; •• theprincipleofrepetition; •• breadthandsimplicity; •• truthfulnessandreliability;
The law	An objective, necessary relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • fundamental laws; • • take into account the limits of
The ory	A reliable form of scientific knowledge about a set of known objects that is a system of interrelated statements and proofs and includes methods of explaining and predicting events in a particular subject area [147].	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •• objectivityandscrutiny; •• adequacy and completeness of the description of objective reality; •• interpretability; •• realityandreliability; •• an integrated system of facts, concepts, hypotheses and laws; •• The principles of complementarity and conformity as criteria for the interdependence of new theories.

In the structure of scientific knowledge, first of all, there are two levels of knowledge - empirical and theoretical. They correspond to two interrelated but at the same time specific types of cognitive activity: empirical and theoretical studies

[62]. Empirical and theoretical are philosophical and general scientific categories that describe the main forms and levels of scientific research.

The empirical level of knowledge is knowledge derived directly from experience and is related to the processing of the properties and relationships of the object being studied. It always provides a level of theoretical knowledge. Theoretical is the knowledge gained through a degree-thinking system. At the empirical level, vivid thinking (emotional cognition) predominates; the rational method and its forms have the following meaning. Therefore, the object under study is mainly reflected in its external connections and appearances, is convenient for thinking and expresses internal relations.

Empirical research is directed directly (without intermediate connections) to its object. Using techniques and tools such as comparison, observation, measurement, experimentation, it processes the object under artificially created and controlled conditions (including mental), assimilates it by analysis, induction, and so on.

The theoretical level of scientific knowledge is characterized by the superiority of the rational moment and its forms (concepts, laws, and other aspects of thinking). Theoretical cognition reflects events and processes in terms of their internal connections, understood through the rational processing of empirical cognitive data. This processing is done using “high-order” abstract systems - concepts, conclusions, laws, categories, principles, and so on.

Empirical and theoretical levels of knowledge differ in the subject matter, tools, and methods of research. In fact, these two layers of knowledge constantly interact and are organically interconnected. Their interaction is based on the practice of expanding all aspects and levels of cognitive activity, uniting their various aspects as a result of new knowledge.

The generally accepted classifications of empirical and theoretical methods of scientific knowledge are given in Table 3.

The growing role of science in social development, its penetration into all spheres of people's lives, the quality of training of future professionals depends on

the direction of research in the educational process. An important aspect of it is the formation of research skills in the future specialist, which makes it necessary to provide students with an approach to life, profession, self-research.

Table 3.

Empirical	Назарий
<p>Observation is the purposeful and organized perception of objects and events related to the solution of a particular scientific problem.</p>	<p>Analysis is the division of a research object into its components.</p> <p>The combination of elements obtained in the synthesis-analysis.</p> <p>Comparison-Determining similarities or differences of objects.</p> <p>Abstraction is the mental isolation of the basic properties of an observed object.</p> <p>Modeling (as an activity and a result) is a mental or material system that reflects the object of research.</p> <p>Induction-individual inference.</p> <p>Deduction-transition from general to private.</p> <p>Analogy is a method of comparing knowledge about one object with another.</p>

An analysis of the experience of higher education institutions in terms of our study allowed us to draw the following conclusions:

- The complexity and mastery of new types of educational activities is a key element of the educational process, which determines the personal growth of the future professional, his formation as a specialist;
- professional and personal qualities are necessary to prepare the student for research activities, which are formed in the process of integrated education;

- The system of research skills determines the self-education of the personal qualities of the specialist necessary for effective professional activity.

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